

BOND CLAUSE FOR FRP REINFORCEMENT IN THE FUTURE EUROCODE 2

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ABSTRACT

The future Eurocode 2 (FprEN1992-1) is under preparation and a draft version is already published. It has been a strong wish, that new materials like fibre reinforced concrete or non metallic reinforcement are introduced in this design code. The main issue in design of embedded FRP reinforcement is the differing modulus of elasticity. In addition, there are some material specific properties like the linear elasticity and the different long-term behaviour which have to be considered. This all has been done for most design cases. Here the different bond and anchoring behaviour is addressed. The main failure modes are splitting as well as pull out. Especially for dense reinforcement in laps and end anchoring sections which are under higher loads a safe limit has been defined to avoid splitting. For less dense reinforcement the approach for steel reinforcement has been modified and calibrated by a database with more than 120 lap splice tests. It could be shown that the ModelCode2020 as well as the prEN1992-1 2020 D7 approach can be adopted till a certain bond length. The main difference is that the transition to degressive behaviour is modified to a smaller value. Another difference in the bond clauses is that the pullout is not treated as a concrete property only. While the maximum bond strength the concrete can manage is known and is only weakly time dependent, the bond behaviour of fibre reinforced reinforcement is a function of time, temperature, stress, geometry and material of the bar surface. Here has to be shown that the designed anchorage or lap splice length does not lead to a long term failure. The author explains different possibilities to fill this gap with test methods and discusses the clauses at different examples.

KEYWORDS

Bond test; beam end test, bond creep test, FprEN1992-1

INTRODUCTION

There is a wide range of FRP-materials for the internal reinforcement of concrete. Main difference is the material and the way of manufacturing. While in the choice of materials a combination of 50-75% of mostly unidirectional high strength fibres with a resin is used, for the bond a much greater spectrum of manufacturing concept has found the way into the market. Here manufacturers chose concepts like sanding, indentations, geometrical grooves as well as combinations of the different possibilities. Nevertheless, all rebars available on the market show a bond strength for the commonly tested bond lengths not far from the one of reinforcing steel. For longer lengths the knowledge gets is somewhat reduced. The same issue can be stated for the long-term resistance of bond. For this paper a review of the available literature for long embedment length as well for long term loading has been performed.

General Bond Clause

In the current Eurocode 2 EN1992-1 [1] the general bond clause is defined by the following set of equations. It has to be stated that for standardized reinforcing steel with a defined rib geometry and a defined projected rib area f_R the basic design bond strength is defined mostly by the concrete strength.

$$f_{bd} = 2,25 \eta_1 \eta_2 f_{ctd} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

With:

f_{bd} is the design value of bond strength

η_1 is a coefficient for the quality of the bond condition and the position of the bar during concreting

η_2 is related to the bar diameter: $\eta_2 = 1,0$ for $\phi \leq 32$ mm

f_{ctd} is the design value of concrete tensile strength

The basic required anchorage length, $l_{b,rqd}$, for anchoring the force σ_{sd} in a straight steel bar is defined in the equation from EC2, 8.3 as:

$$l_{b,rqd} = (\phi / 4) (\sigma_{sd} / f_{bd}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$l_{bd} = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3 \alpha_4 \alpha_5 l_{b,rqd} \geq l_{b,min} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

With:

l_{bd} is the design anchorage length

α_1 is for the effect of the form of the bars assuming adequate cover

α_2 is for the effect of concrete minimum cover

α_3 is for the effect of confinement by transverse reinforcement

α_4 is for the influence of one or more welded transverse bars

α_5 is for the effect of the pressure transverse to the plane of splitting

σ_{sd} is the design stress of the bar at the position from where the anchorage is measured from

For different applications as end anchoring (l_{bd}) or lap splice (l_0) different factors can be applied, to take into account the different geometrical and mechanical conditions of bond. The factors $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_6$ are fixed in tables with national determined parameters. All factors are taken as 1 for no positive effect. That means if no further information is known or considered, the most conservative embedment length is calculated. This is different for the lap splice where different factors greater than one can be applied for different diameters and percentages of the lap.

In fib model Code 2010 [2] for the first time a full parametric bond clause has been introduced. In fib bulletin 72 [3] the background of these parameters is widely explained and discussed. In this project extensive bond tests with concrete steel have been performed all over the world using the beam end test, direct tension tests as well as standard pullout tests according RILEM RC6 [4].

$$f_{stm} = 54 \left(\frac{f_{cm}}{25} \right)^{0.25} \left(\frac{l_b}{\phi} \right)^{0.55} \left(\frac{25}{\phi} \right)^{0.2} \left[\left(\frac{c_{min}}{\phi} \right)^{0.25} \left(\frac{c_{max}}{c_{min}} \right)^{0.1} + k_m K_{tr} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

f_{stm} is the design stress of the bar

f_{cm} is the concrete strength =

c_{min} is the minimum concrete cover

c_{max} is the maximum clear concrete cover

k_m describes the effectiveness of the transverse reinforcement

K_{tr} is the normalized ratio of transverse reinforcement

To determining anchoring length i.e. development length, tests with less idealized bond behaviour like the beam end test, where the test section is not under compression load, are taken into account and deliver more accurate predictions than the standard pull out test.

From this more scientific background a somewhat simplified and adjusted equation has been developed for the FprEN1991-1

$$l_{bd} = k_{lb} \cdot k_{cp} \cdot \phi \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{sd}}{435} \right)^{n_b} \cdot \left(\frac{25}{f_{ck}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left(\frac{\phi}{20} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot \left(\frac{1,5\phi}{c_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \geq 10\phi \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

With:

k_{lb} is 50 for persistent and transient design situation, 35 for accidental design situations

k_{cp} is the coefficient for casting effects on bond (1,0 for good conditions...)

c_d is the minimum of concrete cover and half of the bar distance

In the enquiry version the n_σ has been taken as 1 for bar stress less than 435 MPa. For higher values a value of 1,5 is defined. This exponent takes into account, that longer bond lengths are less effective than shorter lengths. In earlier drafts of the prEN1991-1 n_σ was taken as 1,5 for the whole range of stress. To simplify this equation for “normal” reinforcement steel and to bring some more safety into short embedment lengths a value of 1 has been proposed n_σ for σ_{sd} smaller than 435 MPa. This means till the embedment length is proportional to the stress to be anchored till a value of 435 MPa. For higher stresses the length increases overproportionate

FRP Rebar Bond behaviour

For FRP reinforcing bars totally different anchoring concepts with different bond behaviour are used. In some guidelines a minimum bond strength is defined. It can be stated that for the different surface preparations shown in Fig. 1 different bond-slip curves are expected and achieved: [5]

Figure 1: different surface preparations of FRP rebars

In Fig. 2 the different failure behaviour of different other rebars is shown in a simple pullout test. It could be shown, that the bar which looks most like a conventional steel rebar shows a totally different failure behaviour. Instead of a shearing off of the concrete corbels (like for reinforcing steel) the bar ribs are sheared off. For a better stability the rib base of the ribs has been broadened and the rib angle is decreased. Indeed, the rib was much more stable in this case. But another unfavourable failure mode came now to the fore. Splitting can be handled with confinement through bigger concrete cover. But this is not the aim of FRP reinforcement which seems to need nearly no concrete cover through its corrosion resistance. In the following rebars have been developed, with a bond behaviour similar from reinforcing steel.

Figure 2: Different geometries with different failure behaviour

As these different surface geometries can cause totally different failure modes, they also cause different bond stress/slip laws for these different cases. It must be stated, that these geometries are no longer on the market, but different applications have been made which are still under service. In addition, new or modified bars are introduced with different surface preparations.

Another point is the question if the bar is pulled out of the concrete through sustained or dynamic loads. What is the load which can be sustained for a lifetime? Can this be tested by a smaller/shorter specimen? Do we have a constant load over the whole length of the embedment length? Are there sections where the bond is overloaded? Are these overloaded or failed sections playing a role for the safety of the embedment length. If not a zipper like failure cannot be excluded. This last question can be called “robustness” of bond.

Bond clause for FRP reinforcement

There was the strong demand to use a similar approach for FRP reinforcement as for steel reinforcement. This was difficult for the old linear bond law with a constant design bond stress f_{bd} over the whole embedment length. As now a parametric nonlinear approach has been chosen for steel reinforcement, the parameters have to be adjusted, only.

Influence of the single parameters

In a detailed analysis performed by Caspari at the TU Kaiserslautern for three different GFRP materials as well as for B500 concrete steel the influence of concrete strength, concrete cover, bond length, confinement and confining pressure have been researched. As test specimens beam end as well as standard RILEM pull out specimens with $5d$ length had been used [5]. The first question which have been researched is the influence of the concrete strength. The results are shown in Fig. 3. For these tests the maximum bond stress for a $5d$ diameter length is seen as a criterium. All tested materials including the standard steel reinforcement steel show increasing bond strength with increasing concrete strength in the range which is described in MC2010 [2] as well as in the prEN1992-1. It seems, that the increase is somewhat smaller for higher strength concrete. Possible reasons can be the smaller compressive modulus in transverse direction as well as the smaller shear resistance of the resin.

Figure 3: Influence of the concrete strength on bond strength

A similar test series has been performed with the different materials in a beam end test setup researching the influence of the concrete cover. This is depicted in figure 4. It seems that the influence of the concrete cover is similar or somewhat greater than for concrete steel. In addition, it seems that the old approach from the recent Eurocode 2 on α_2 (α_2 was not defined to be different than 1 in Germany) defines a better description for all materials including reinforcing steel than in the current draft of the standard.

Figure 4: Influence of the relative concrete cover c/d_m

The next series in figure 5 shows the influence of the diameter. This series is performed using three different diameters in the smaller range 8-16mm. This smaller range gives a little less information as for concrete steel is already used a smaller rib area f_r . The surface preparation is also reduced for GFK 1 and 3. For bigger diameter a similar behaviour is expected. The reference diameter in model code is 25mm and 20mm for prEN1992-1. Here a planned tests series with bars in bigger diameters, which is already planned at this time, can give more information.

Figure 5: Influence of the bar diameter on the maximum bond strength

The most interesting influence to determine the embedment length from the issue of design is the influence of the bond length. Here the functional interaction between longitudinal stiffness and the bond slip law in typical geometrical situations is important. This influence is shown in figure 6 for steel and the three FRP rebars used in this study. For smaller embedment lengths up to 14 times the diameter all curves show a good fit with the equation proposed in prEN1992-1.

Figure 6: Influence of the bond length between 5 and 14 ds

Another important conclusion for detailing can be drawn from beam end tests with a different degree of confinement. All FRP rebars show better performance with more perpendicular reinforcement. This effect is even bigger than for concrete steel. A possible reason for this behaviour is the somewhat higher splitting action, which can be converted into confinement or perpendicular pressure through a higher perpendicular reinforcement. Reinforcement steel shows here a smaller effect as the splitting action is somewhat smaller.

Figure 7: Influence of the perpendicular reinforcement

The analysis of the different single parameters has shown that most influences are in the same range as for concrete steel. We see the same dependencies in the same directions, and it is a simple conclusion that the new non-linear parametric approach is “as it is” already better than the linear approach of “old” EN 1992-1 [1]. Now the question arises if this is the case also for longer embedment lengths and practical members in end anchoring or dense lap splice situations.

Behaviour in full sized members

This analysis is not done for the three types of reinforcement researched in the first part of the paper which was mostly performed by Caspari, but for all types of reinforcement described in available scientific papers and own tests. As end anchoring is less researched and much more difficult to test than lap splices, the author has put a focus on lap splices. As the prEN1992-1 does not distinguish between these cases, all conclusions have been drawn from these tests. Therefore, a database of 128

tests from more than 15 papers has been set up. In the following diagram (figure 8) all results are depicted with the maximum bar stress against the embedment/splice length in the test. With the colour the different papers can be found. Generally, a trend the higher the bond length, the higher the transmission of forces can be stated. Due to the different products, conditions and concrete strength in the tests the scattering is high. In most test series for a certain geometry only one or two additional parameters are varied. So often for one length different results are to be seen. This is not only caused by the scattering of the tests but also because of the different surface geometries, concrete strength and additional conditions like perpendicular reinforcement, bar sizes, reinforcement ratio, slab or beam geometry and other influences.

Figure 8: Overview on all lap splice tests of the database

The next diagram (figure 9) shows the data grouped into confined and non-confined tests. In addition, already a diameter, concrete strength and concrete cover compensation has been performed. In this special case the performance has been expressed as strain in the bar. From this diagram a strain limit could be defined for unconfined tests. Generally, the confined tests show a better behaviour. Higher strains can be withstood without or with later spalling of the concrete.

Figure 9: Rated performance on all 128 lap splice tests of the database

In figure 10 all tests are shown together with different approaches. The black line shows the linear behaviour between embedment length and transferable load. It could be shown that even more pronounced longer embedment lengths are less effective to increase the transferable load. In the last version of prEN1992-1 this linear curve is followed to a stress value of 435 MPa. After this point a transition to a nonlinear description (exponent 1,5) is proposed.

The green curve describes the approach used in the D4 version of prEN1992-1 for concrete steel. Here for lap splices a 1,2 times higher load must be taken into account instead of applying a factor for lap splices. Even for the green curve many tests are lower than this limit.

So, a further modification had to be proposed: This is a simple linear equation till a value of 217 MPa which is the half of the transition value of reinforcement steel. The second part of the curve uses the same exponent as reinforcement steel for values greater than 435MPa. So only the transition stress value had been changed to form a safe and practical equation for the embedment/lap splice length. All other influence exponents described in the universal bond and splitting equation had been checked and left unchanged.

Figure 10: Performance of 128 lap splices and evaluation through different approaches

There is still another point to be addressed here: Long-term resistance of bond.

If splitting does not occur the pullout (long term or short term) is the relevant failure mode. For this purpose, long term tests must be performed in wet concrete under sustained load for every specific product. A possible test setup is shown in figure 11. Important is that the load is constant over the time. This can be achieved here by a sufficiently soft spring setup, a lever arm construction or a hydraulic hollow piston. From these tests a long-term bond strength must be determined, which is the second condition for the bond. (Pahn and Caspari [5]) have shown that the values are different for each FRP rebar. Together with the long-term resistance of the bar a robustness of bond must be shown to exclude a zipper like failure mode under sustained loads (abZ 1.6-238 [6])

Figure 11: Setup for bond tests under sustained load

All clauses discussed here are valid only, if the bond stress is smaller than the long term bond strength.

CONCLUSION

It could be shown, that the known influences on the bond performance also hold true for FRP reinforcement. The performance can be described with the same modern approach as for reinforcement steel. Concrete cover influence is not perfectly included and described. Here product specific approvals or the old approach from current EN 1992-1 [1] can solve the problem.

The modifications in FprEN1992-1 for FRP in the Annex R takes into account for the smaller modulus by making a transition to a under proportionate approach at a stress of 217 MPa instead of 435 MPa. The higher spalling effect for FRP rebars is taken into account through a strain limit for unconfined splices and anchoring of 0.006. A second check, that the long term bond strength is not exceeded, has always to be performed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request